

THE OXIDIZED CHOLESTEROL STRATEGY

By Scott Davis

The Oxidized Cholesterol Strategy™ PDF eBook Download Free

Is your relationship with your partner declining daily? Do you lack motivation? These are some of the key signs of clogged arteries. While a diagnosis is important, clogged arteries do take a toll on your life. When poorly managed, they can even lead to serious heart disease, stroke, and even death.

So far, many remedies available to the regular public have only been band-aid solutions, with medical professionals only tackling the symptoms and effects of the condition. However, there have not been many efforts to eliminate the disease permanently. Well, only the rich have managed to get access to a permanent solution!

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The program teaches you how to target and unclog your arteries finally, allowing you to go back to a healthy, happy, and fulfilled life.

This breakthrough program teaches you how eliminating one hidden ingredient from your diet lowers cholesterol below 100 and clears out up to 93% of clogged arteries. The program will even help you prevent stroke and heart attacks.

According to the official site, using the Oxidized Cholesterol Strategy, you will learn the following:

- Permanently and thoroughly clean out the plaque built in your arteries
- Reduce cholesterol levels to a healthy level
- Boost physical and mental energy levels
- Improve sexual energy and libido
- Promote better mood

The Oxidized Cholesterol Strategy comes in a digital form as an eBook and features a detailed systematic guide that teaches you how to unclog your arteries and maintain a healthy cardiovascular system. The Oxidized Cholesterol Strategy is born from extensive research and is even backed by several scientific studies published by prominent authorities, including the National Center for Biomedical Information (NCBI).

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Scott Davis, who has extensive experience in the field, authors the book. He has spent decades researching various related topics and even

published other successful health programs. Additionally, the Blue Heron Health News Site publishes the Oxidized Cholesterol Strategy. The news site is a popular publisher of countless health programs, books, articles, and guides that have gone on to be successful and helped millions of users in the US and across the world.

When it comes to the Oxidized Cholesterol Strategy, what makes this program special is its all-natural design. Unlike conventional medicine, the program does not call for the use of any drugs, chemicals, supplements, or even invasive procedures. Everything is done naturally by simply making small changes to your daily diet. Therefore, you do not have to worry about putting toxic chemicals into your body or using habit-forming drugs you will have to stick to for the rest of your life!

It is also important to note that the Oxidized Cholesterol Strategy is not just another regular program you find online to help you curb the symptoms of clogged arteries. Instead, it combines the expertise of the author and years of research to give you a permanent solution. Using this program as directed guarantees full and permanent unclogging of your blocked arteries. Yet, even with its impressive functionality, the program is affordable, making it easily accessible to anyone.

This Oxidized Cholesterol Strategy review takes a deep dive into everything to know about the program – including how it works, its benefits, and its costs. The detailed review helps you decide if the program is for you or not.

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What is the Oxidized Cholesterol Strategy?

The Oxidized Cholesterol Strategy is a digital eBook program written by Scott Davis and designed to teach you how to unclog arteries. The program comes in a systematic guide with instructions you can follow on eliminating one key ingredient in your diet.

Now, it is a known fact that clogged arteries interfere with blood circulation. On the other hand, blood circulation is an important lifeline of the body. After all, every single cell in your body relies on this function to receive its nutrients and oxygen as well as remove wastes.

Therefore, to restore effective blood circulation, you have to solve the problem of clogged arteries. This is exactly what the Oxidized Cholesterol strategy is made to do!

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How Does Oxidized Cholesterol Strategy Work?

The Oxidized Cholesterol Strategy works by teaching you how to unclog your arteries by making a small change to your diet. This program debunks the main existing myths about plaque buildup, which is what helps to solve the problem from the root cause.

The first myth is that bad cholesterol, LDL, is the cause of plaque buildup. Now, this could not be further from the truth. In fact, according to the official site, when you examine several LDL level results from people with clogged arteries, you will notice that some

have high cholesterol (LDL) levels while others have normal or low levels.

Nevertheless, they are all at risk of suffering a heart attack. Another untrue myth is that reducing cholesterol levels using medication can prevent heart attack. In fact, a study conducted by the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) and the New England Journal of Medicine in 2008 shows that treatment with two statins was more effective at lowering cholesterol than treatment with one statin.

However, treatment with two statins also leads to a higher buildup of plaque in the arteries. This means that while drugs may seem to be effective in the beginning, they ultimately aggravate your condition further. After all, while the drugs help to keep your cholesterol levels low, your arteries continue to be clogged. Therefore, the goal should be to clear the arteries instead of focusing on the cholesterol levels.

So, what is the root cause of clogged arteries?

The same iron rusts when in contact with oxygen block arteries. This explains why LDL levels alone are not enough to cause clogged arteries.

Here is how it works – for example, patient A has 150 LDL cholesterol levels while patient B has 350 LDL cholesterol levels. Now, patient A may have 80% of their LDL oxidized while patient B only has 5% of their LDL cholesterol oxidized. Therefore, while patient A has a lower LDL level, they will still suffer from more severe clogged arteries than patient a will will, even though they have a higher cholesterol level.

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This oxidized cholesterol drills itself into the arteries and causes inflammation among other damages. Therefore, it is important to note that it has only oxidized LDL that builds up on the arterial walls and not regular LDL. Furthermore, bad cholesterol (LDL) can be oxidized but good cholesterol (HDL) cannot.

According to Scott Davis, every organic product oxidizes when in contact with oxygen. These include fruits (bananas brown when exposed to air), milk (goes sour), and meat (mold builds up). On the other hand, fat goes rancid. Small amounts of oxidized fat spread the oxidations around the arteries and create plaque buildup.

So, what is the solution to eliminate rusted clogged arteries?

Different oils have varying oxidation properties. So, some may become highly oxidized before you start to feel the effects. This is much more prevalent among highly processed oils you buy at the supermarket.

Unbeknownst to many people, oils such as sunflower and safflower are the most oxidized while butter, coconut oil, and olive oil are much healthier. As a general rule of thumb, high saturated fats like butter and coconut oil are almost impossible to oxidize.

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The Oxidized Cholesterol Strategy takes this approach to help you tackle the problem of clogged arteries and oxidation.

Here is how it does so:

- The program features a four-week strategy to completely eliminate the plaque buildup in your arteries and prevent a stroke and heart attack.
- It teaches you exactly which foods because oxidized cholesterol and which reduce it. This means that you do not stick to some boring, calorie-limiting diet – you will be impressed with how many delicious foods are safe to consume!
- It offers a week-by-week guide toward unclogging arteries and tackling oxidized cholesterol
- It gives the user tools to monitor and manage your strategy to make sure you succeed.

Here are the complete contents of the Oxidized Cholesterol Strategy:

Part One: Introduction

The first section looks at what cholesterol is the traditional view of cholesterol, and the objection to the traditional view of cholesterol.

The second section takes a revisionist view of cholesterol, the process of oxidation, and oxidized cholesterol. You will also learn the sources of oxidized cholesterol, including diet, endogenously produced oxidized cholesterol, and LDL particle size.

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Lastly, you will get a detailed overview of the adverse health effects of oxidized cholesterol, including how it inhibits ABCA1 and LxR receptors, increases thromboxane, and sphingomyelin production, and inhibits prostacyclin. It also includes how diseases like diabetes, Alzheimer’s and dementia, and arthritis may stem from oxidized cholesterol.

Part Two: Dietary and Lifestyle Habits That Promote and Inhibit Fat Oxidation

The first section focuses on statins, their ineffectiveness, and their side effects. The second section looks at antioxidants like vitamins A, C, and E, flavonoids, uric acid, curcumin, and capsaicin.

The third section covers anti-inflammatory agents like vitamins, and minerals, like selenium and magnesium. It also looks at omega-3 fatty acids, monounsaturated fats, flavonoids, and fibers. You will also find a section on dietary fats and oils, including vulnerability to oxidation, rules for the consumption of dietary fats, desirable dietary fats, permissible dietary fats, and undesirable dietary fats.

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Part 3: the Four-Week Plan to Reduce Cholesterol and Prevent Coronary Artery Disease

Lastly, the third part focuses on the actual solution to clogged arteries. The section shares a detailed weekly plan for the program. You will even find rules for resistance training and sample exercises.

The second week also shares meal plans and prep, sugar and grain substitutes, recipes, and an exercise program. The second week focuses on aerobic exercises, outlining its rules and samples. The third week focuses on meal plans and prep, concentrating on good and bad oils, recipes, and exercise.

The fourth and final week also shares meal plans and prep, recipes, and focuses on meat and dairy along with their substitutes. You will also

find an exercise plan outlined. However, the program does not end there. You will also find Mediterranean diet meal plans, including breakfast, lunches, snacks, and dinners.

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What Are The Benefits Of Using The Oxidized Cholesterol Strategy?

- Permanently and thoroughly clean out the plaque built in your arteries
- Reduce cholesterol levels to a healthy level
- Promotes cleaner and efficient breathing
- Restores blood circulation
- Boosts physical and mental energy levels
- Improve sexual energy and libido
- Improves your mood
- Helps you improve your eating lifestyle for the better

Pros of Oxidized Cholesterol Strategy

- Available in digital and physical book
- Reasonable 60-day money-back guarantee policy
- Backed by scientific research
- Designed to work for all adults and genders
- Works even for healthy people who want to improve their quality of life

Cons of Oxidized Cholesterol Strategy

- Restricted to people under 18 years old, nursing and pregnant women
- Exclusively available for purchase from the official site

How Much Does the Oxidized Cholesterol Strategy Cost?

The Oxidized Cholesterol Strategy costs you \$49. As soon as your payment is approved, you will have instant access to the digital eBook. If you want, you can also receive the physical book at an extra small fee and zero US shipping fee. The payment for the program is a one-time affair so you do not have to worry about any repeated costs or subscription fees. You will even receive free updates on the program in the future.

The Oxidized Cholesterol Strategy is available for purchase from the Blue Heron Health News site alone. Therefore, you will not find it listed on other platforms, not even Amazon. This is done to ensure you receive the authentic product and enjoy other exclusive customer benefits.

Customer benefits include a 60-day refund policy, a secure payment gateway, and access to customer support.

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Conclusion: Oxidized Cholesterol Strategy Reviews

The Oxidized Cholesterol Strategy offers a pretty safe and effective method to eliminate arterial clogging finally. However, this is not all that makes it special. In addition to its affordability, the program is sustainable and 100% natural. Therefore, beyond its four-week plan, it is even a good option for healthy people who want to maintain a healthier eating lifestyle that benefits their cardiovascular system.

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